

Implementation of Democracy in Tertiary Level: A Case Study of A Private University

Taiyeba Marzuka Shamma

(Department of Civil Engineering, Sonargaon University, Bangladesh)

ABSTRACT: *The concept of democratic classroom is new in Bangladesh. Most of us are unaware of the chemistry of democracy and education. Democratic classroom is very efficient to help students to get prepared for an active citizenship in a democratic society. Democratic education is a type of teaching method through which students gain some social skills. Through democratic classroom they get the touch of liberty of a democratic society. In this study, the implementation of democracy is studied at tertiary level, which is based on a casual comparative design. A self-developed questionnaire has been used in the study to examine the perceptions of 31 students of a private university of Bangladesh. Among the participants. 16 were male and 15 of them were female students, they were from 4 different departments. Data was collected through multiple choice questions, likert type scale and the data was analyzed through simple statistic study and MS Excel. Through the study it was found that most of the students felt that they have classrooms which resemble democratic classrooms as they considered that they enjoy 'liberty' in their classroom activities.*

KEYWORDS –Democracy, Education, Classroom, Society, Liberty

I. INTRODUCTION

To build up a democratic society the first attempt that is required is that the citizens are participative, active and have sense of justice. Educational institutions can be taken as industries to prepare such types of individuals who can run a society in a democratic way. There are a number of studies which explored the need to develop such approaches through different types of pedagogical approaches to build up students who can become participative, active and responsible citizen who can take over the command to rule tomorrow's society.

Such an active concept of education can be developed in a democratic classroom environment. Democratic classroom not only helps students to learn according to the curriculum but also helps them to develop their academic success simultaneously in terms of social skills development. Democratic classroom creates an effective and supportive learning environment in which students learn how to become useful to a society, how to take responsibilities and also to fulfill them. Democratic classroom has emerged from the principles and practices of democracy and how it is used in the field of educations. Therefore, the concept of democratic classroom provides a rich and a comprehensive educational system that enriches the lives of children in every aspect (Ahmed. Said & Jusoh. 2015).

1.2 What is Democratic Education System?

Democratic education system is such a unique teaching and learning method where students get the freedom to ask questions, to share ideas, to question the social injustice and inequality. In democratic classroom students have the right to argue, to disagree, and to give defensible reasons and they also have the right to give explanations. This is the place where they learn to take negative opinions or comments cordially and try to understand others' point of view.

Democratic education is an educational system in which democracy is considered both as a goal and also as a method of instruction. It helps to bring democratic values into educational system. Democratic education system includes self-determination within a community where all are considered as equals. Some values like justice, mutual respect, mutual trust and patience are also included into democratic education system. It tries to ensure that students voice become equal to the teachers (Cartwright. 2004).

1.3 Definition of Democratic Classroom:

Democratic classroom is a place which offers individuals appropriate environment for thinking and provides opportunities to express or share their own ideas freely without any kind of hesitation. It is very important to express ideas (Turabik & Gun, 2016).

The term "democratic education" is synonymous with the term "Freedom-based education" just like democracy as a political system is used to ground individual freedoms, in educational system also democracy is used to ground individual freedom. This is the freedom for students to learn freely, to decide what they study, how they study and when they study (Morrison. 2008).

Democratic classrooms motivate students academically and it also empowers them in such a way that they become socially responsible, as a result active citizens come out of them. This process starts in the classrooms and it flows eventually into the communities or societies. Democratic classrooms help students to develop their social skills, ethics and also their character. It creates the opportunity for students to make themselves prepared for facing the real world waiting for them. Apple and Beane (1995 in Solmitz's 2001. P. 36) stated some conditions which are important to turn an ordinary classroom into a democratic classroom.

Some of those conditions are, for example-

- Open flow of ideas that help people to be fully informed as possible.
- To have faith in the individual and the capacity of being collective while solving problems and to come to a conclusion.
- To think and analyze critically and to evaluate ideas.
- To be concerned of others' welfare and the common good.
- To be concerned of the dignity and rights of individuals and minorities.

1.4 Benefits of Democratic Education:

The students can gain a lot from democratic education system, because it allows students to be free enough in case of learning, thinking, expressing and sharing ideas. It never pressurizes students for anything. In a democratic classroom students are always welcomed with what they have, what they are in real life. It helps the critical thinking disposition of students. Democratic classrooms help students to be curious, to analyze their thought to determine their goals. They also learn to search for alternatives; they learn how to defend their thoughts reasonably. Through democratic classrooms they also become open to new ideas, to be honest to what they want and all

together it help them to think from different perspectives. Students get both formal and informal education through this (Turabik and Gun. 2016).

Democracy and freedom based education helps students with autonomy and choice which give them the chance to experience a much different and much better quality of education than that offered by traditional, conventional education system. Democratic education promises an opportunity of more meaningful learning. When students get the chance and freedom to learn on study what interests them or what they want to they become more engaged in it and less alienated from their studies. More engagement to studies means better retention, better critical analysis and better critical reflection. When students are given freedom to take decision about what they want to do. It increases their independence, it stronger their interests and it also helps to develop the quality of their work.

Democratic education system has noinfantilizing effect, rather, it creates confidence in the heart of the students and they get the ability to rise to the challenges. Through this process students become more self-dependent, more mature, self-disciplined, confident, honest and intrinsically motivated. Ultimately there students become better democratic citizens, because they have inherited the techniques of how to negotiate with others, to know themselves and to face obstacles. (Morison. 2008)

1.5 Statement of the Problem:

In Bangladesh most of us are of laid back nature. Here people usually mull over and talk about almost every problem that goes around us, which almost all of us experiences every day. But people hardly do anything to solve those problems (Hossain. 2006). The problem stated above is a common scenario of our society. This happens because people over here rarely raise their voice and they are hardly seen to ask any question when things go wrong around them. Being quite day after day has become a habit. Now if classroom is taken as microcosm of a society, then the students will be considered as the members of the society.

Sometimes in classroom it is found that students are less interested to listen to others opinion, but they are eager to state their own opinion. This way there arises some issues related to the dissatisfaction of the students who were not able to share their views. So eventually some problems come up with these types of issues. Now if we think about future then these students are going to be the future citizens, if they do to change their act then the future of the society is in danger.

To avoid such dangers the students must be taught to act democratically in their classroom. They must learn to collaborate with others, just like the way people act in a democratic society. As students spend a certain amount of time in their classroom so it is a good place to give the students a democratic environment. Through this they can learn to handle situations with care and to be cooperative with the other members (Engelhard. 1939).

1.6 Research Questions:

The questions stated below are some important issues which need to be solved. In this research solution of these questions are searched.

1. What are the behaviors teachers demonstrates in classrooms to build a democratic classroom?
2. What are the types of freedom that teachers allow students in classrooms to build a democratic classroom?
3. What types of opportunities are provided by teachers to build democratic classrooms?

1.7 Significance:

In a country like Bangladesh where people practice collective values and questioning the authority is almost forbidden, here to have the practice of democracy in classroom is a bit tough. But it is not impossible, because, classroom is the place from where the students can be thought to live life in a different way. In a classroom they can learn how to question and how to bring change to the traditional society.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Education empowers a nation, and if education is united with democracy than it works much better. In a classroom, democratic education is needed but that democracy must be a deliberative democracy. It is important because in a deliberatedemocratic classroom each students gain the same importance.

2.1 Education for Deliberative Democracy

In "Education for Deliberative Democracy" by Martin Samuelsson. 2017, he conducted his research on "Education for deliberative democracy" and he tried to investigate it through classroom discussion. Democracy alone is not that much powerful as it is when it is practiced in a deliberative way. Deliberative democracy helps citizens to gain some skills, attitudes and values. Through democratic education system students can be taught how behave in a society, how to behave in classroom in a deliberative democratic way. The data for this study was collected during the spring and autumn term of 2014. The method of data collection was qualitative, and the main interest of this study was an in-depth investigation of classroom discussions. Three schools were visited: all of them were located on the west coast of Norway. Students from different grade levels were selected to collect data as well as different subjects. Among the three schools one school had a religions foundation, while the other two did not. Data was collected basing on different types of classroom discussions. The first one was the explorative discussion this is a type of discussion with pervasive disagreement but with a little striving toward consensus. This fulfills both the reason giving and the reflective requirements. The second one was the problem solving discussion, this is such a type of discussion with a clear striving for consensus but with little disagreement. The third one was the predetermined discussion- this is a type of discussion reacting a conclusion, while showing some instances of disagreement. In the final discussion requirements of deliberative democracy was fulfilled. Three smaller discussions 1) How to continue working with the topic? 2) Whether students should be assigned to sides randomly? 3) What the topic of the data should be? In this discussion students freely shared their ideas, they chose the sides they support; they argued, different points of views were also presented, they listened to others and reflected upon each other's arguments and reasons, and finally they reached a conclusion. This is what a democratic class should be like, so this type of discussions is perfect to turn any classroom into a democratic classroom.

2.2 The Relationship between Teachers' Democratic Classroom Management Attitudes and Students Critical Thinking Disposition.

These two are very important elements of a democratic classroom. In the study conducted by Turabik & Gun. 2016. they investigated "the relationship between teachers' democratic classroom management attitudes" and students' critical thinking disposition". These two are very important elements of a democratic classroom. This is because, students need to realize or feel what type of attitudes their teachers are showing towards them. If teachers are positive, let them become free and let them speak up, then it can be said that they are willing to or they might turn the class into a democratic class.

In their research, they studied 530 students from public high schools located in Altindag district of the province of Ankara, Turkey. They used tools called "Democratic Classroom Management scale" developed by Demits and "Critical thinking Dispositions Inventory" by Akliyik to collect the data. For analyzing the data they used t-test, Anova, Pearson correlation and simple linear regression analysis. They conducted the study during the spring term. In their research they used the relation scanning model to analyze the teacher student relations, they approached with qualitative techniques. Through their research was found out that the views of the student about their teacher attitudes are at moderate level, and it was also same according to gender. So they have a similar view. But, views about democratic classroom management varied depending on class level, family income level and education level of parents. As the level of the class went high students participated less to the opinion about their teachers, attitude of democratic class management. The students whose family incomes are low think more critically than the students whose family income is much higher. Their age was also a matter.

2.3 Democratic School Culture Perceptions of Sport High School Students

Students find democratic classroom quite good as they got the freedom they started to utilize it and gradually they found out that this was helpful to their studies. Enes in 2016, researched on studying democratic school culture perceptions of sport high school students. Through this study he tried to put light on student's perceptions about democratic school culture. It is important to make students realize the necessity of their point of view or their opinion regarding their education system. They must be realized what they are doing; how they are doing; what they want and what they are getting. The opinions may differ according to age or grade levels or socioeconomic condition of the students. In this study there were 216 participants who were students studying at sports high schools in Sakarya and Batman Provinces of Turkey.

For this study the Democratic School Culture Perception Scale (DSCPS) was used to collect the data. When estimated the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of the scale was 92 only. For analyzing the data, Mann Whitey U and Kreskas Wallis H tests from non-parametrical tests as well as descriptive statistical techniques were benefited from. Students from different grade levels were selected for the study. 81 male and 63 female students from Batman Sports High school were selected, and from Sakarya Sport High school 53 male and 19 female students were selected for the study. The students studying at sport high schools had positive perceptions about democratic school cultures. Their perceptions did not differ according to gender. The democratic school culture perceptions of the students studying at 10th class were more positive than the students who were studying at 9th class. It can be said that class of less aged groups attributed to but dimensions less, when on the other hand when classes became upper those attributions increased. This happens because when students grow up their awareness level increases. Democratic school environments affect both teachers and students in various positive ways.

2.4 Relationship between Democratic and Social Skills Development of Students

Democratic classroom not only helped the students in their studies but it also developed their social skills. Through this they got chance to improve their attitudes towards the classroom and to the society also. Ahmad, Said, & Jusoh in 2015, studied regarding "The relationship between democratic and social skills development of students". Through this study they have tried to figure out how the relationship should be between democratic classroom and students and how the social skills of the students are developed through it. But basically the aim of this paper was to find out the effect of democratic classroom environment on developing the social skills, of the students. This research is based on casual comparative design and this study also used a self-developed questionnaire to examine the participants. 80 male and female students were selected to conduct this

study. They were selected basing on random sampling from 20 secondary schools in one district of Khyber Pkhahtunkwa. Pakistan.

For analyzing the data chi-square test was applied. The concept of democratic classroom is not only about democracy in education rather it is connected to many other important things that a person should learn. One thing that one must keep in mind is, that classroom is a version in miniature of a society where the students find opportunities to lay the foundation to become an active citizen. In this study researchers found that there was no significant difference in the perceptions of males and female secondary students regarding the effect of classroom environment on developing their social skills. They equally considered democratic classroom environment important for their social skills development. The study showed that democratic classroom has positive effect on all the three social skills: listening to others; waiting for turns; and raising hands to ask questions. The students perceived that democratic classroom environment played great role in developing their foundation of being a good citizen. This not that these three are the only social skills which are needed to be developed, but as told before that classroom is a miniature of society so students must act, in classroom like citizen of a society. In this way they can experience more of a democratic society.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Participants:

The participants of this study consisted of 31 students from University of Liberal Arts Bangladesh (ULAB). 16 of them were male students and 15 of them were female students. Participants were selected from 4 departments: those are Computer Science and Engineering, Bachelor of Business Administration, Media Study and Journalism and Department of English and Humanities. This study was conducted during the spring semester of 2017 academic year.

3.2 Data Collection tools:

Data concerning the implementation of democracy in tertiary level were obtained using the likert type scale where items were made up of the choices:

- 1) Strongly disagree.
- 2) Disagree.
- 3) Neutral.
- 4) Agree
- 5) strongly agree

Another type of method that was used for collecting data for this study was multiple choice questions where items were made up of the choices:

- 1) Yes.
- 2) No.
- 3) Others (Sometimes).

The last type of question that was used for data collection was an open ended type question. Two questions were given and participants were set free to answer whatever they wanted to write. So in this research 3 types of data collection tools were used within a single survey questionnaire.

3.3 Data Analysis:

Data were analyzed through using simple statistics studies and MS Excel. To determine the result descriptive statistics were done. In the analysis of the data normality test was performed to get normal distribution of the data.

IV. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Table of Questions-1

SI. No.	Question	Yes	No	Other
1.	Are you given chances to give your opinion	25	3	2

	in class?			
2	Are your opinions given priority?	22	2	6
j.	Are you welcomed in decision making	19	6	5
4.	Do you ask question in classroom?	20	6	4
5.	Are your questions answered?	21	1	8
6.	Do you debate with your teacher?	9	15	6
7.	Are you given chances to explain your opinion?	20	4	6
8.	Do you think about any matter from different perspectives?	19	3	8

In Table no.1, multiple choice questions were given regarding students opportunities to take part in a democratic classroom. For example question 1 was about if they were given any chances to give their opinion in classroom. Among 30 students 25 students said yes; 3 students said no and 2 students said sometimes. In question no 2 they were asked if their opinions were given priority. In this question 22 students said yes; 2 students said no and rest of the 6 students said sometimes their opinion are given priority. Then they were asked if they were welcomed to take part in decision making. Here 19 students said yes; 6 students said no and 5 students said sometimes they are welcomed to take part in decision making. Then the students were asked that do they ask questions in classroom. In answering this question out of 30 students 20 said yes; 6 students answered in negative and the other 4 students said that sometimes they ask questions. When they were asked that whether their questions are answered or not 21 students said yes; only one student said no and the rest of the 8 students agreed that sometimes their questions are answered. After that the students were asked about whether their questions are answered. Then the students were asked about their interactions with their teachers. They were asked whether they debate with their teachers when something controversial comes up while they were studying, in answer 9 students said yes; 15 students said no and the rest of the 6 students said sometimes they debate with their teachers. When the students were asked about the chances they get to explain their opinions the class, or the opportunities they get to make others understand what the students think of it. 20 students said yes; 4 students said no and the other 6 students said that sometimes. In question no 8 the students were asked that if they consider or think over any matter from different perspective. To answer this question 19 students said yes; 3 students said no and 8 students said that sometimes they think over matters from different perspectives.

In this table all the questions were about the opportunities which a student must get in a democratic classroom. They must get the chance to give their opinion in express what they think about any matter. This gives them the chance to make their voice heard. For any democratic classroom, or democratic society, making people to hear their voice in very essential.

Another, important point is about asking question in classroom. For a democratic classroom it is very natural that students should get the chance to ask question about anything that seem wrong to them, or that attracts them. Their questions should be answered too, otherwise they will become demotivated both in asking questions and also in seeking problems. This demotivation might pull them back from being an active, participative citizen of a democratic society.

Debating with teachers is not a bad thing at all. If the students are debating over a valid reason or something relevant there is nothing wrong. But it must be done in a respectful way. Another important thing is students must get the chance to explain their opinions. This is good for everybody in the class, because, when someone explains their opinion he or she clarifies their point of view and this is helpful to make others better understand the matter. When someone explains

something so many other topics come up there and students get the chance to know a lot about other things just than the topic itself.

4.2 Table of Questions-2

SI. No.	Question	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	You are encouraged to give your opinion	1	3	4	17	5
2.	You have the chance to argue with others	1	6	6	13	5
3.	You listen to others opinion	1		4	16	9
4.	You help each other in classroom	1	2	7	10	10
5.	You are active in sharing classroom activities			9	13	9
6.	You are active in sharing classroom responsibilities			8	12	8
7.	You wait for your turn to share your view	2	2	8	10	9
8.	You hold your patience when others speak		1	4	19	6

In this Table no.2, 5 point Likert type scale has been used to collect data. Here the questions were of such type which gives students a chance to evaluate themselves regarding their act. Through their acts it will be showed that how much democratic their classes are or whether there is any practice of democracy in their classrooms. Here in Likert scale each point stands for:

- 1) Strongly disagree. 2) Disagree. 3) Neutral. 4) Agree. 5) Strongly agree.

In the first question students were asked if they were encouraged to give their opinion. In reply 1 student strongly disagreed; 3 students disagreed; 4 students stood neutral; 17 students agreed and the other 5 students strongly agreed. Then in the second question the students were asked if they get the chances to argue with others. In reply 1 student strongly disagreed; 6 students disagreed; 4 students were neutral; 13 students agreed to it and the other 5 students strongly agreed with it.

In the third question the students were asked about listening to others opinions. Here 1 student strongly agreed to this; 16 students normally agreed to this; 4 students just stood neutral and the rest left strongly disagreed to listen to others opinions. Then the fourth question was about helping each other in the classroom. To this question 10 students strongly agreed; 10 students simply agreed; 7 students was neutral; 2 students disagreed to this and 1 student strongly disagreed about helping other students in the classroom. When the students were asked that whether they were active in sharing classroom activities. 9 students strongly agreed to this; 9 other students stood neutral and the rest of the 13 students agreed in sharing classroom activities.

Next the students were asked about sharing various responsibilities of the classroom. For this question 2 students simply disagreed to share any types of classroom responsibilities. 8 students kept themselves neutral; 12 students agreed in sharing responsibilities, and the rest of the 9 students strongly agree to share the responsibilities of a classroom. After that the students were asked about waiting to let their turn come to share their view with others. Through this question it

come to light that 2 students disagreed about waiting for their turns to come; 8 students kept themselves neutral about waiting; 12 students agreed that they wait for their turn to come and the rest of the 8 students strongly agreed to wait for their own turns to come to share their views with the other people in the class.

Then finally in question no 8 the students were asked whether they hold their patience when other students speak in the classroom. In this question 6 of them strongly agreed to that they hold their patience while others speak. 19 other students simply agreed about holding their patience in classroom, 4 students just stood neutral to it and the one left disagreed about holding patience for his or her turn to come when someone else speaks in the classroom.

The question in this table gave students a good chance to evaluate their democratic movement. Through this test it can be easily seen that how much democratic their classrooms are or how much practice of democracy they have in themselves. As it is said earlier that classroom is a microcosm of society so it is better to start practicing democracy as early as possible. One of the questions here is about encouraging students to give their opinions in classroom. Encouraging students to give their opinion is as important as giving opinion in a community meeting. This is because if everyone does not give their own opinion and only few people take the chances to command the society, it will no more remain a democratic society. Autocracy will grab the society.

Another crucial issue about democratic classroom is to help each other in classroom in classroom activities. This helps to create a bonding among the students and it is also a good scope that they become close to each other. When they will grow up they will also need to act like this in a society, they will have to work together for a perfect democratic society. Sharing classroom responsibilities is also a big deal to be carried out in a democratic classroom. Sharing classroom responsibilities helps students to take trials for sharing the responsibilities of running a community or a society. If student are taught about taking responsibilities and fulfilling them from an early age then it will be helpful for their future life, it will be also a great source of experiences.

Teaching students to wait for their turns to come to share their own points of view is very essential for running a democratic classroom. For a democratic society it is essential that the members of the society wait for their own chance or turn to come and share their ideas or thoughts with others. Through this way everyone gets the chance of speaking equally and nobody is deprived from sharing his or her ideas.

Another important issue of democratic classroom is holding patience while someone else is speaking. It is a bit tough for most of the students to hold their patience or to control their emotion when the other speaker is speaking. It is a matter of self-control and it is also a means of showing respect to others. It is also a type of help, it is like helping others to let them talk freely without any kind of interruptions. It is every one's right to express their thought or their feeling to other people around them. And it is everyone's duty to make sure that they hold their patience and make a chance for others to deliver their speech without any obstacles.

4.3 Table of questions-3

In Table 3 the first question was about how fairly the teachers use to treat the students in the classroom. Here out of 30 students 10 students disagreed about fair behavior of the teachers in their classroom. They individually had many reasons to disagree about this. According to some students teachers have some students according to their own preferences. Another student wrote that some teachers treat some specific students very well, because they are closer with the teacher. Some other student wrote that some teachers behave well with those students who have good grades and can speak English fluently. They also wrote that students who are not that much good are

always dominated by the good students and sometime they are made fun of. They feel inferior in the classroom.

Some other students wrote that the teachers need to be more neutral to the students and keep the weak students in consideration. The students think that their teachers should take more care of the weak students and it will be helpful for them if they talk with them softly to make them feel good. There were 5 students who stood neutral about this question, they wrote that all the teachers are not the same, but there are some teachers who need to be more student oriented or student centered. They think that if the teachers behave in a neutral way then it will be good for everybody in the class, and students can act more freely. This will also help to reduce the gap between the students and the teachers. The rest of the 15 students agreed that the teachers' behavior was fair enough and they treated everybody equally. All the students use to get treated fairly in the classroom and all of were happy about their grading. They wrote that students were being helped by the teachers according to their need, and teachers were also eager to solve out the problems they were facing. Teachers use to help the weak students as much as they can and they also guide the good students so that they can do even better. Some students wrote that their teachers are so friendly with them that they (the students) feel so free to ask about anything that is causing problem in their study. The student can even share about their personal problems if they need to. To them their teachers has always been a guardian like figure on whom they can rely on, whom they can trust.

The second question was about how matters are dealt when people have different option about same matter. The students were asked how they use to come to a conclusion where situation is like this. To answer this question 4 types of answers were got. Some students wrote that in such situations with different types of opinions they try to rely on what their teacher decided for them. In this type of case the students think that their teachers take good decisions which are fair for all. So they try to cooperate with their teachers and grant the decisions taken by their teachers. According to some other students' decisions in such situations are taken according to the will of majority. So it can be said that majority wins. Here decisions can be taken through voting. Another way to solve out this type of problem is negotiation. Through mutual discussion many difficulties is sort out in classroom. When they will grow up and face the society, they will need to solve many problems by negotiating with other members of the society. This is a good way to act democratically both for classrooms and also for society.

4.4 Discussion

Though this research it has been found that majority of the students had the practice of democracy in their respective classrooms. They were positive, active and participative in various types of indoor activities operated by their teachers. According to the result most of the students were positive in cooperating with the other students of the classroom. A big portion of the students used to give their opinion in the classroom and in return they agree that, their opinions were given priority. There was no significant amount of difference in having positive attitude on feelings towards the democratic environment of their classroom. This research also showed that students were eager in asking questions in the classroom, and their teacher also answered to their question.

In a similar type of study done by Enes in 2016. it was found that students had positive feelings towards the democratic school culture perceptions. In that research also it showed that students actively took part in the classroom activities and they were participative in all types of works. They interacted with their teacher in the classroom they dealt and had an enjoyable classroom environment.

The study done on ULAB's students also showed that the students get enough opportunities to enhance their social skills. For example they help each other in the class: they argue between them, they take part in classroom activities. They also share their activities or work in groups; they

share the classroom responsibilities also. These things are granted as social skills, more over the students also wait for their own turns to come so that others students can give their speech or their opinion without any obstacles or any hesitation. Majority of the students also agreed about holding their patience when someone else speaks. So, watching the result it can be said that most of the students practiced democracy in their classroom.

In a study about developing social skills through democratic classroom by Ahmad. Said & Jusoh. 2015. It is seen that students had a positive effect of democratic classroom on their social skills development. The students highly agreed to the contribution of democratic classroom environment which enhanced their social skills. They highly believed that democratic classroom is a mighty predictor of students' social skill development. The students believed that it also helped them to improve their behaviors which are more suitable for a democratic classroom. They had a practice of democracy through this research.

V. CONCLUSION

5.1 Advantages:

The purpose of this research was to examine the implementation of democracy in tertiary level. The research concluded that the general perception of the students studying at University of Liberal Arts Bangladesh were quite positive. After analyzing the data it was seen that the students of University of Liberal Arts Bangladesh got a touch of democracy in their classroom. Though it is true that all the students were not getting the same facilities but still most of the students had an opportunity to act as a citizen of democratic society in their classroom. Through this study it was also seen that students had opportunities to develop some of the social skills in their classroom.

The development of social skills via democratic classroom is nothing new. But it never lost its value. The concept of social skills and democracy is related to each other. This happens like, if someone is practicing democracy then he or she must have some individual attitudes to act in the society. There are various ways of practicing democracy, but it is better it start it through the system of education. An education for democracy may become a crucial method of teaching future citizens how to establish arguments; how to underpin them with reasons; who to listen and reflect upon others" speech and to come to a conclusion with collective opinions. All of these criteria can be practiced within a classroom, because classrooms are miniature society (Samuelsson. 2016).

5.2 Limitations:

To state the limitations of this study it can be said that the time was short. If there were availability of time, the study could be both qualitative and quantitative. More interviews could be taken if there was enough time. Another problem was that in general, most students were not aware of the concept of democratic education system, so it was tough to make them understand the topic first, then to interview them.

5.3 Recommendations:

In a country like Bangladesh, where traditionalism is practiced almost 'die heartily,' it might be difficult to establish democracy in classroom. People living here are rarely interested to question the authority. As a result autocracy is 'grabbing" us. But things cannot keep going like this. Change is needed, if we want to bring the change then we must change it from the core. It can be started from the classrooms, it can be the classrooms of schools or of tertiary level. Classrooms are the places where students spend a large amount of time. So, classrooms should be turned into democratic classrooms. There they must be given the chance to question the wrongs of the society; all of them must feel equal; they must have the chance to argue; to disagree; to share their opinions and also to listen to others opinions. Students' questions must be answered, they must be welcomed

in decision making and their opinions must be given a priority. If classes go like this then it can be hoped that when these students grow up. They would bring change to the society.

5.4 Possible Application:

The process of democratic classroom can be used for various purposes for example, like character education, moral development, civic education, group learning and so on. Democracy in classroom can also be used for a notion or an approach to reform the social organizations and the members of the society. Democratic education can help to create effective citizens for the society through providing the students opportunities to better understand and to analyze all the interplays of our democracy, social development, education, social responsibilities, and also to develop social skills and to fulfill the commitments to serve and to develop or to improve the society. The system of democratic education helps the student to think freely, to make their voice heard without any hesitation. It provokes them to raise their voice for social justice and to ask question about anything which goes wrong.

5.5 Conclusion:

Democratic education system affects students in positive ways and it also inspires them to contribute in practicing democratic attitudes and behaviors. Democratic education increases the awareness of matters of the students related to their lives and the environment, so that when they face the real world they do not get afraid or confused. This also helps to increase the levels of their "fiction" which are related to democracy (Samuelsson. 2016).

An atmosphere provided by democratic classroom environment may deliver positive social experiences to the students. On the other hand the functioning systems of the non-democratic or traditional education systems may affect the students negatively. It may even lead the students to turn into an aggressive, fearful or passive individual. Classroom may become examples of democratic culture through making such classroom environments where students get the chance to learn democratic life and where the students can learn with their own experiences.

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